

Investigating Corporate Editors in OpenStreetMap

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In recent years, OpenStreetMap (OSM) has evolved from a Volunteered Geographic Information Project to one of the most successful Geospatial Crowdsourcing Platforms. Volunteers, governments, and corporations all make contributions to its global map. Corporate editors (CEs) are the latest entrant in the OSM ecosystem, and their prolific contributions have drawn significant interest from the OSM community as well as the scientific community. In 2018, the OpenStreetMap Foundation introduced a set of Organised Editing Guidelines to address large scale editing such as the ones made by CEs [1]. Despite the guidelines, there is a perceived lack of dialogue and transparency between corporations and the larger community. Previous research has focused on the changing landscape of OSM users with the growth of CEs, cataloguing the global footprint of corporate editing and the map features edited by CEs [2]. Others have studied the impacts of having a dedicated workforce capable of making significant changes to specific map features in a short period of time [3-5]. This study focuses on the CEs themselves. While other research has explored the impacts of CEs' existence, they have not explored who these editors are, and the reasons and conditions for their employment. We sought to learn about the demographic makeup, careers, motivations and community relationships of these individuals. With these objectives, we created an anonymous, 28 question mixed methods survey that was distributed directly to every listed CE account provided in accordance with the Organized Editing Guidelines on the OSMwiki. The results of this survey indicate that there is a correlation between CE job satisfaction and their involvement in the OSM community, and that there is variety in the demographics of the CE population, in the tasks they complete, in the way they interact with the community, and the way they perceive OSM itself.

The response rate to the survey was low as many employers prevented their employees from taking the survey. Thus non-exclusive groups were created based on the responses, previous literature, and our research objectives. Group 1 was composed of corporate editors who were paid an hourly wage (n=20), dubbed the "hourly CEs". Group 2 were editors who are paid an annual salary (n=2). In a similar vein to the hourly CEs, these editors were named the "annual CEs". The juxtaposition of the hourly and annual CEs allowed us to determine what factors contribute to greater job stability, if there is a difference in the way these two groups edit in OSM, their motivations for working in OSM,

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and their interactions with the community. Group 3 was made up of corporate editors who mapped in OSM prior to their employment (n=16). They are labelled the “veterans” due to their experience with OSM. This allows exploring whether prior experiences with OSM are considered an asset and provides additional information on OSM editing as a career since it can be determined if veterans are frequently responsible for the more involved and responsibility-based tasks, such as validation of the edits. Group 4 was composed of editors who edited the same region of the map as their residence (n=10). This group was designated the “locals” as they provide an insight into the value corporations associate with local knowledge and expertise of their corporate editors. These groups were then compared to each other using ANOVA and compared to the population using t-tests in R.

A non-exclusive typology was also created to allow for further analysis of results. This typology was based on the statistical distribution of answers to several matrix questions in the survey (for a full list of survey questions, please see the link in the appendix). The questions were related to the editing behaviours, interactions with community members and community events, and job satisfaction of the CEs. A cumulative score was calculated for each matrix, and any respondents who fell one standard deviation above or below the mean was sorted into the relevant type. The following types of CE were created: heavy (high frequency, high variety edits at work, n=6), light (low frequency, high variety edits at work, n=6), technical (high frequency, high variety mapping technique users, n=6), sporadic (low frequency, high variety mapping technique users n=6), social (high variety, high participation in community related activities, n=5), less social (high variety, low participation in community related activities, n=4), happy (high variety, high satisfaction, n=6), and dissatisfied (high variety, low satisfaction, n=4). These types, paired with the groups created based on literature, allowed for a multi-pronged analysis.

The t-tests indicated that hourly CEs communicated with other OSM users through chat channels like telegram much less frequently (p=0.044). While this is the only method of communication with the community that was significantly different, it should be noted that three of the four remaining communication methods all had p values below 0.15, implying that communication with the community is not done with much frequency across this group. The statistical tests also revealed that annual CEs edit on their own time (p= 0.006), edited the map prior to working as editor (p=0.045), and edit and create roads (p=0.046) and amenities (p=0.029) at a significantly greater rate than the population mean. Annual CEs assigned significantly less importance to learning about OSM and geospatial data (p=0.031) and building technical skills (p=0.025, n=2). Annual CEs participated in global state of the map conferences with much more frequency (p=0.029). They were well below average in their belief that they were learning valuable skills (p= 3.916e-09, n=2) and did not plan to build a career in editing OSM (p=4.994e-09). Annual CEs had a greater number of differences compared to the other groups, but their size (n=2) relative to the population (n=44) is much smaller than any other group. It is also not surprising that this group participated in global state of the map conferences as their familiarity with the community would make them more aware and perhaps more enticed to attend such an event. The only difference between the veterans (n=16) and the population was that they were significantly more likely to participate in regional state of the map conferences (p=0.041). The veterans’ increased likelihood to participate in regional state of the map conferences makes sense as they have increased familiarity with OSM and its community.

The locals made considerably less edits to natural features at work (p=0.004). There

was a strong sentiment of wanting to continue working on projects involving OSM, exceeding the population mean ($p=0.037$). The lower frequency of editing natural features by the locals may have been due to sufficient data already existing within OSM in these regions, or a lack of prioritisation of these features from the corporations who employed these editors. Wishing to continue working in OSM could be explained by the fact that 60% of this group considered improving local data to be very important.

Through ANOVA, we learned that hourly CEs differ from annual CEs ($p=0.0174$), veterans ($p=0.0114$), and locals ($p=0.0274$) for editing amenities when at home. This group also differed from annual CEs ($p=0.0185$), veterans ($p=0.0086$), and locals ($p=0.0351$) for editing building footprints at home. The trend continued across all 12 measures for at home mapping activity. All editors belonging to the annual CEs and the veterans mapped in OSM on their own time, and 90% of locals did so as well. In comparison, only 30% of hourly CEs mapped in OSM on their own time, which would account for why there was a significant difference between this group and at least one other for every question involving at home editing. Hourly CEs differed significantly from locals for editing administrative boundaries ($p=0.0347$) at work. This was likely due to the fact that locals edit on smaller regions – the main characteristic of this group was editing where they work – which limited the range of their editing activities, while over 68% of hourly CEs did so on a global scale.

A profile of a typical CE was created using the mode of each question's response which revealed a general framework of their work week, with 8-hour days (19.5% of respondents), one project meeting per week (62.5% of respondents), and good relationships between colleagues (51.6% of respondents). This profile also revealed that the typical CE lived in North America (63.6% of respondents), worked full-time (88.9% of respondents) with their employer of at least 12 months (21.4% of respondents), at their first paid OSM editing job (81.0% of respondents) where they are paid an hourly wage (60.6% of respondents). On a daily basis they edited all over the world (50.0% of respondents), used JOSM for most of their editing (68.4% of respondents), traced satellite imagery (50.0% of respondents), corrected the shape of geometric objects (51.4% of respondents), validated existing features (42.8% of respondents), and corrected the attributes associated with features (42.8% of respondents). If they require assistance, they consult with coworkers through internal channels (91.4% of respondents), consult the OSMwiki (88.6% of respondents), or discuss the challenge with coworkers (85.7% of respondents). Most did not map in OSM before their employment (56.8% of respondents), but started contributing to the map once a week (62.5% of respondents) on their own time. They often participated in mapping parties (32.2% of respondents), but otherwise rarely participated in other community events. They would like to continue to work in projects involving OSM (58.1% of respondents), enjoyed working with the coworkers (51.6% of respondents), wanted to continue a career in mapping (48.4% of respondents), and feel that they learned valuable skills at their jobs (45.2% of respondents).

Comparing the heavy and light type CEs revealed some of the nuances of corporate editing. Though these two types represent the greatest and least amount of editing, light CEs have greater job security, with 75% paid monthly compared to 83% of heavy editors being paid hourly. This may also be due to light editors' increased exposure to OSM, as these editors both mapped before they were hired to do so (60% of type) and mapped on their own time (80% of type). These differences likely suggest that there are a variety of roles for CEs, some of which do not entail editing itself. The idea of different roles is also supported

through the comparison of technical and sporadic users, as both used a variety of techniques, but again we saw a disparity of editing times (1-8 hours a day for technical CEs compared to 0-1 for sporadic CEs). Sporadic CEs were limited in the frequency and variety of mapping techniques used because they had limited opportunities to use them. Contrary to the heavy and light editors however, both the technical and sporadic types were paid mostly hourly, with rates of 50 and 60%, respectively. There was significant overlap between community involvement and job satisfaction within CEs. 80% of social CEs are also happy CEs, and less social editors make up 50% of the dissatisfied type. Less social and dissatisfied editors are fairly homogeneous, all working full time, paid hourly, not mapping in OSM before they were hired, nor mapping on their own time, and living in North America. In comparison, social and happy CEs had an even split of employment styles, with a mix of full time, part time, and freelance workers, who lived in four different regions around the world. They all mapped in OSM before their hiring, continued to map on their own time, and they find their work to be exciting or engaging. While it is unsurprising that having interest in your work leads to greater satisfaction, the results of this survey showed there is undoubtedly a connection between satisfaction and mapping in OSM outside the workplace, as well as in engagement with the community.

Unfortunately, we encountered several challenges in reaching out to individual editors as the organisations they work for explicitly prevented them from answering the survey. This had a significant impact on our ability to collect responses, as over half the CE community was made unavailable to this study. Over the course of this research, we reached out to 34 corporations and 1985 CEs, receiving 39 complete responses and an additional 5 usable partial responses. This represents a response rate of 2.2% meaning that we must establish that our results do not serve as a definite representation of CEs. Low participation was also the rationale for the multi-pronged analysis, as we sought to learn as much as possible from a limited population. Though all CEs reserve the right to not participate in this study, the blanket refusal seen by some corporations is at odds with the autonomous agency which has been a tradition of OSM. At one company, all direct messages sent to any of their CE accounts on OSM redirect to the inbox of their manager, which raises similar questions. While our results may not provide a faithful representation of all CEs, our work furthers conversation regarding these workers and broaches the topic of their agency.

Survey questions, statistical analysis, figures, and a list of contacted corporations are available at: <https://github.com/Hoferek/Investigating-Corporate-Editors-OSMScience-2024>.

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